

TRUBLO 3rd OPEN CALL
Crowdfield Companion Evaluation Report

Smart Farming and Climate Action: knowledge transfer and stakeholder reputation in multi-disciplinary innovation ecosystems.

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Executive Summary

This report describes the course of the Crowdfield Companion TRUBLO project over 9 months between 2022 and 2023, the project leads had proposed that the use of decentralised ledger technology (DLT) as a solution to the problem of reputation-making in multi-disciplinary research-oriented innovation ecosystems and to build digital trust between actors with no previous physical interaction. The study describes the emerging requirements for knowledge-transfer and validation tools in the dissemination of proven know-how and the capture and rewarding contributions and specific actions taken in the context of climate action in two distinct grower communities: pioneers in regenerative farming practice and urban re-wilding activists.

VIN-Q is a participative research ecosystem supporting knowledge sharing and building together the practices for regenerative shift for wine-growers started in Catalonia, Spain. VIN-Q supports the dual needs of academic scientists to validate and transfer their results and methods to real sector and end users, and the needs of the farming community to learn and share emerging knowledge proven to support collective transition to regenerative viticulture practices taking into account local and regional features.

Urban Hedgerow, is an urban re-wilding community in central Dublin. It brought together disparate local actors, residents, expert and amateur gardeners, and property owners to identify and repurpose underutilised urban spaces that may be 're-wilding'. The first area selected, was on top of a single-story carpark where a 73m portable, native species 'hedgerow' that would provide food and shelter for urban pollinator populations. The project specifically serves the pollinator needs first and is largely unknown and unseen by the wider community.

The study describes the context of multi-disciplinary innovation ecosystems and describes how decentralised technologies can be deployed to address stakeholder reputation, trusted information and governance within early-adoptive, high-impact innovation ecosystems.

Keywords—*distributed ledger technologies, mobile wallet, non-fungible tokens, smart farming, ecosystem innovation, stakeholder reputation, digital trust, knowledge-transfer, climate-action.*

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I. Introduction

In industry and agriculture the climate challenge is to transform input-heavy systems and make them more sustainable, efficient, less wasteful, with better management and improved methods. In agriculture and land management further challenges exist such as widespread soil depletion and desertification alongside other outcomes of climate change and human intervention (eg. overuse of fertiliser and weed killer), all the while feeding more people with fewer resources including water, land and biodiversity.

The Crowdfunder Companion (CFC) Project is a consortium market-discovery initiative led by agri-innovation SMEs: Origin Chain Networks and Agriledger. The research was supported by the Next Generation Internet TRUBLO funding strand of EC Horizon 2020. The project explores Net Zero agri climate response efficiency, and seeks to support the agri-food sector to achieve science-based net zero targets and transition to regenerative practices at scale.

What does it mean to establish effective climate-neutrality and net-zero conditionality in the context of a food system or value chain? Where does lifecycle assessment start for a bunch of grapes or a bottle of wine? In current analyses, food systems have an indirect impact on sustainability and net-zero targets and yet Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) describes how UN Sustainable Development Goals and other cooperative alliances have high expectations for the future of food, and positive social outcomes [1]. For example, zero net emissions is a target enshrined in the EU's climate law [2]. (The European Green deal is the roadmap for the EU to become climate-neutral by 2050) [3].

Klaus Schwab, Founder and Executive Chairman at the World Economic Forum, describes how with the Great Reset of the Globe after the COVID-19 pandemic, we are observing a growth in reliance on location-based solutions. This is evidenced by the strides in edge computing and the proliferation of smart devices such as mobile and IoT (Internet of Things) [4]. Yet a recent report from EU Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2022 notes the trend towards progress but points out that digital skills, SMEs and 5G networks lag behind [5].

It is our contention that the livelihood of food producers and the effective climate-neutrality of production are predicated on empowering the food value chain with information and connectedness. Affording stakeholders in the holistic food system opportunity of access and reward for contribution to qualitative and quantitative data (process, state, objects and things) is key to a progressive future food

system [6] in the age of ubiquitous computing and convergence [5].

II. Trusted knowledge-transfer and participatory research

Establishing reputation and credibility in emerging knowledge domains is key to establishing mutual understanding, common purpose and cohesion. Willingness to transfer knowledge represents cooperative behavior and cooperation is more likely when strong third party ties exist around a relationship.

In cooperative food systems choosing what information is shared, by whom and for what purpose is key to formalising knowledge transfer pathways, establishing reputation and motivating engagement or action. Strong ties to mutual third parties are a source of motivation in dense social networks, the third party offers oversight and accountability. Reputation and cooperative norms are two reasons why strong third-party connections promote cooperation [7]. Cooperative norms may also limit competition.

Competition inhibits cooperation and knowledge transfer. Successful knowledge transfer increases competition between actors as they can risk becoming surplus to requirements, and losing reputation. Potential for increased competition is a powerful rationale to avoid sharing expertise.

In this section we take a closer look at the context of digital information and knowledge-transfer in common-purpose, climate-active, multi-disciplinary ecosystems.

A. Expert knowledge and climate impact

The shifting context of expert or trusted information on the internet is multifaceted. TWG Landscape Report: Trusted Information Standards references three main reasons why trust has become increasingly significant since the end of the 20th Century [8].

1. Social differentiation: contemporary societies are increasingly differentiated (different beliefs systems, division of labour). Only to a limited extent can individuals directly verify information they receive. We have become more dependent on what others claim to be true.

2. Complexity of scientific methods: A special case is the 'epistemic division of labour' or the Knowledge Economy. Scientific methods, so complex as to be opaque to

non-experts (experimental research, analysis, or simulations and AI models). However, the fact remains that numerous conclusions, many with commercial implications are based on scientific method.

3. Information and information technology (IT): IT significantly increases the amount of information generated and distributed or shared across the globe. A trend that will likely increase due to the latest advances in Generative Artificial Intelligence. IT decouples information and context. Individuals cannot reasonably be expected to rate, on the basis of their own experience, how true or trustworthy the information they discover is.

What does expert knowledge in a climate-facing holistic food system signify? Unsurprisingly, it depends on who you ask. Stakeholders in the VIN-Q project describe the knowledge held by stakeholder groups adjacent to their own, from whom they could immediately see the benefit of learning, held high reputation as holders of expert knowledge.

Growers in the wine region of rural Catalonia, expert viticulturists and wine makers, chose agronomists with sustainability credentials as their most desired sources of information: stakeholders who understand the business, culture and social needs of the farming community who could advise them on specific issues and remediation strategies to the benefit of their own commercial farming practices.

Agronomists and advisory service providers, whether they had sustainability certification or not, identified scientific researchers as their most desired sources of expert knowledge: stakeholders who had the means to evidence and quantify environmental impact.

Scientists, aware that environmental measurement is a contested and imprecise field, sought further study and validation of novel methods with the addition of technical means to complete tests and source data at significantly large scale to quantify impact in statistically relevant numbers.

Local authority stakeholders with ambitions to deliver on digital transformation goals specified ‘an enhanced farm advisory service’ with asynchronous, bespoke query responses as the optimal framework for learning and trouble-shooting climate response. They had all the information they needed in their archives. What they desired was a way to query and extract aggregated data and to identify consistent measurable patterns. They valued the knowledge of technical providers, in particular Artificial Intelligence (AI), IoT and computer vision experts, with the added requirement of consent and cooperation from growers, all while being accountable to democratic governance processes.

The VIN-Q project is one of two case study cohorts collaborating with the CFC project, the other being a smart cities biodiversity initiative called Urban Hedgerow.

The CFC project needed to identify and support these diverse communities, with competing internal points of view, and extrapolate common requirements. It was also predicted that with the successful growth of the ecosystems,, diverse concerns would morph, change and grow.

Overall the stakeholders sought to cooperate to (i) co-create exploitable outputs (primary and complementary secondary); (ii) validate reputation and trust in an autonomous cooperative ecosystem and (iii) maintain and evolve trust relationships via social networks and influencer partnerships with an emphasis on cohort transition to regenerative commercial and net-zero practice.

B. Knowledge transfer in multi-disciplinary ecosystems

The CFC project targeted multi-disciplinary experimentation and learning ecosystems and set about gathering requirements and scoping out infrastructure that would support their common aims.

These open innovation networks sought to co-design field-tests, trial new technologies, define new methods and valorise important practices with the common purpose of identifying and disseminating climate-smart solutions within their cohort and potentially more widely.

Scaling and accelerating dissemination of successful methods was key to understanding the strategic aims and common purpose of these communities.

The CFC project offered a trusted information framework for sharing both human and computationally sourced data. The DLT-enabled infrastructure would empower landowners, food producers, and climate scientists to accurately, and verifiably engage with App content / data and to earn a reputation for themselves as App users, and community contributors. CFC sought to provide a crowd-sourced, anonymised overview and validation framework for knowledge and practice as it emerges within the ecosystem.

C. Stakeholder reputation in emerging knowledge domains - understanding influence.

Crowd-sourced reputation modelling is a relatively new field that emerged with the advent of ubiquitous, mobile computing. Geolocated data-points, shared asynchronously between highly mobile individuals in locatable, yet fully virtual communities afforded the opportunity to crowd-source reputation with rating schemas for places, restaurants, venues, retail and all sorts of experiences. Crowd-sourcing news from the frontlines, crowd-sourcing reputation with testimonials, enhancing online discovery

with anonymously sourced, but credibility-rated inputs from engaged users [9].

In this research we focus on ubiquitous mobile and edge computing interfaces to facilitate diverse reporting methods and facilitate models of trust in multiparty cooperative systems and elaboration of a collective reputation-making model that is transparent, incremental and context-aware.

For human resourced inputs we follow a simple three-phase trust life cycle proposed by Ruohomaa and Kutvonen [10].

1. Initializing a trust relationship: The trust life cycle begins from determining an initial trust in participants and choosing the appropriate participants for the collective's requirements.

2. Observation after initialization: Identifying diverse means to observe participant engagement. An active member of an organization may take on a leading role in the collective. [11]

3. Evolving reputation and trust: User reputation can be updated based on previous actions, and this information can be used to inform recommendations to other parts of the collective.

There are many potential stakeholder engagements through which to elaborate this life cycle. Onboarding non-technical users with frequent low connectivity at the edge is an important context. The skills required to participate and contribute in a decentralized cooperative ecosystem are non-trivial.

Individuals who actively engaged with either of the two CFC case studies were considered to be early-adopters, and aligned themselves with one or more of the following archetypes or roles (Table I). The project archetypes represent sets of commonly-valued behaviours in hybrid climate-smart learning communities and offer an insight into the common characteristics of participants.

TABLE I. STAKEHOLDER ARCHETYPES - EARLY ADOPTIVE ARCHETYPES. SOURCE: PERSONAL ENGINEERING AND MARKET DISCOVERY. SOURCE: OCN (2022)

No	Characteristic, motive and voice			Archetype
	Characteristic	Motive	Voice	Persona
1	Bias to action	Individual	Loud	Activist
2	Considered	Group	Loud	Champion
3	Authoritative	Group	Show and tell	Expert
4	Reknoned	Group	Vocal/loud	Leader
5	Knowing	Group	Vocal	Advocate
6	Present	Individual	Quiet	Participant
7	Engaged	Individual	Quiet	Learner

No	Characteristic, motive and voice			Archetype
	Characteristic	Motive	Voice	Persona
8.	Loyalty	Group	Vocal/Quiet	Member
9	Trailblazer	Individual	Show and tell	Pioneer
10	First-to-have	Group	Show and tell	Early-adopter

With a high propensity for early contributors to view themselves as pioneers, highly self-motivated and somewhat performative in communication. Conflicts can arise between the individual's vs. group's aims; the emergence of favoritism or the effect of perceived reputation or 'clout' as a behaviour-changing force in early-adoptive communities is par for the course. Clout is a colloquial term amongst social media users who understand network centrality to signify influence [12].

Network-based models of social capital emphasize the importance of cohesion (the extent to which a relationship is surrounded by strong third-party connections) and range (the extent to which network connections span institutional, organizational, or social boundaries) [7].

Cohesion and range vary across both case study cohorts and both differ in relation to the behaviour on display. In online gaming communities where pseudo-anonymity is common place, strategies for recognising and mitigating disruptive in-group behaviors have emerged. These strategies may include cooperative oversight, the application of boundaries and the transparent application of disincentives and rewards or bounties through gameplay and governance [13].

One example of this in online and virtual communities is the emergence of the reputation token or 'Soulbound token'. A unique, non-transferable proof of some online achievement, perhaps attendance, performance, or ownership of something that took place online [13].

Fig. 1. Stakeholder related data in the CFC App with NFT minting taking place on Hyperledger Besu. SOURCE: OCN (2022)

Fig. 2. Mint and view user sequence: CFC App - POP Profile NFT. SOURCE: OCN (2022)

D. Learn-to-Earn microcredential award system - mobile blockchain application

The Learn to Earn CFC toolkit is a demonstrator for how mobile blockchain-at-the-edge can work to benefit grower communities. Evidencing learning interactions in the ecosystem by tokenizing achievements/actions/state with the issuance of a micro-credential in the form of a Non-Fungible Token or eNFT (Enterprise Non-Fungible Tokens).

Fig. 3. Stakeholder use cases: CFC App. SOURCE: OCN (2022)

Fig. 4. Farmer/grower use cases: CFC App. SOURCE: OCN (2022)

The purpose was i) to demonstrate that field-minting NFTs could reliably happen at the edge, (Fig. 2 and 3), ii), the concept of non-transferable reputation tokens hold value in innovation ecosystems (Fig. 1, 3 and 4) iii) to introduce proof of “Personhood” POP and “Proof of Attendance” POAP concepts to non-crypto native communities. (Fig. 2).

The stack included mobile, cloud and public permissioned blockchain resources, connected via free and open source Metamask wallet. (Fig. 5)

Fig. 5. CFC App - system-view architecture. SOURCE: OCN (2022)

The demonstrator application was built and made publicly available under Mozilla Public Licence 2 [14] in December 2022. The CFC open source resources are available to on CFC Github [15] with an onboarding guidance video [16].

The same processes described here can be used to tokenize almost anything: goods, services, and assets across multi-party systems. Digitising these records in this way can improve ecosystem transparency, valorise engagement and learning, and reward community for participation and loyalty. It is a technology compatible with the aims of

precision agriculture, discussed in more depth in the next Section.

III. Precision agriculture and ecosystem innovation - Crowdfield Companion

Precision agriculture is a management approach that focuses on (near real-time) observation, measurement, and responses to variability in crops, fields and animals. It can help increase crop yields and animal performance, reduce costs, including labour costs, and optimise process inputs. (EIP Agri, Digital Agriculture) [17].

Given the poor network access in mostly remote and rural contexts, we selected a mobile-edge blockchain solution stack with a simple framework and engagement interface for farmers and growers, and scientists and technologists to share knowledge and run experiments.

E. A sense of common purpose

Innovation ecosystems need common ground, a clear mission and strategic direction. Participants need to understand the game they are playing.

Aims:

1. Parallel innovation process across ‘smart farming’ and ‘scientific research’ in the food system and value chain.
2. Accelerated domain-based knowledge-sharing in a digitally transformative mode.
3. Crowd-sourced reputation-building in evidenced regenerative and sustainable agrifood value chains.

Objectives:

1. To initialize interfaces that capture impact data on farms particularly those at the edge or operating off-line and private networks
2. To support functional and efficient data capture to a commercially acceptable degree of accuracy,
3. To test assorted autonomous validation and cross-referencing pathways for human and computational resources in a novel crowd-sourced reputation-making system.

CFC ecosystem virtual community engages grower and farming communities in Ireland and Spain. It motivates participation of the CFC expert stakeholders (including technical, agriculture and environmental domain experts) by offering them the opportunity to co-design and test a reputation-making self-reporting service with high utility in their own ecosystem, engineering new knowledge transfer pathways and defining new value propositions for community generated data, with proven integrity and worth in the food value chain.

To engage with CFC grower stakeholders and to connect them with expert researchers in regenerative and sustainable practices (both academic and industry-led) through the open innovation virtual ecosystem. (Fig. 3, 5).

The first case study was provided by the nascent decentralised science collective VIN-Q, a regenerative agriculture initiative targeting the wine-making industry in Catalonia; the second by Urban Hedgerow a sustainable cities urban greening initiative in Dublin city centre.

Together each project created a community-specific use case for the CFC mobile wallet to demonstrate the benefits and challenges for agri-blockchain in remote and disparate communities.

The mobile CFC wallet provides the infrastructure to deliver a custom-curriculum and certify course completion with a “Learn-to-Earn” credential in a climate-facing knowledge domains.

An important aspect of the study was to bind new knowledge with the advent of ubiquitous, mobile and edge computing on farms, in cities and in landscape management domains.

F. Digital-farmer or digital-grower collectives.

The market opportunity we have discovered is in the enablement of the sharing of trusted information with like-minded individuals, within a defined, common purpose ecosystem and to enable those individuals to build a reputation within their virtual community, based on the engagement and contributions over time.

The CFC App offers a simple, logical interface to gather, share and valorise expert-knowledge, community-updates and self-reported data from grower communities, of diverse scale and purpose (commercial, social, scientific etc...) (Fig. 6).

The mobile architecture deploys a self-sovereign identity paradigm for all users, asserting authorship and ownership of diverse content either published or collected through the App, to the benefit of land owners and land managers. Field-generated digital assets can be created that adhere to standard valid process. The CFC mobile-first infrastructure can secure important field data for posterity and enhance future earning potential.

The infrastructure is flexible and repurposable, offering secure, mobile interfaces for users to self-generate blockchain transaction details as agri-NFTs at the edge.

Fig. 6. End to End process - interactions between CFC App stakeholders. SOURCE: OCN (2022)

Following on from the positive findings for the technical demonstrator and prototyping, it is planned to add a new feature-set to the system functionality to allow users to create virtual assets associated with adherence to Net-Zero-Agri standards, developed in the first instance, with the VIN-Q ecosystem requirements in mind.

The standardisation process will involve engagement at ISO, CEN-CENELEC, ETSI and IEEE to develop an interoperable across technical, trade and regulatory contexts:

- Establishing the framework for longitudinal engagement with land, crop and habitat managers,
- Streamlining knowledge transfer pathways for modules set by scientists and technical providers, that lead to the measurement of natural resources and decisions that have beneficial impact on the diminishing resources of soil, water and biodiversity.
- Specification of data attributes that signify compliance with industry-agreed measures of agricultural practices.

For further content, an introduction to smart farming and open standards infographic is available [here](#) [18].

IV. VIN-Q Case study

G. Describe the mission (common purpose) of VIN-Q

Vin-Q is the wine makers co-creation community that connects producers, researchers and technology providers in a unique sharing knowledge community that facilitates and accelerates the move towards regenerative shift in agriculture [20].

Through collective action in decentralized science, it allows the community to analyze data from multiple sources

and create services and tools to support scientifically validated decision-making in agronomic management.

A unique approach of decentralized science converts scattered vineyards and individual farms with different soil conditions and distributed across different microclimate zones into a coherent research infrastructure that allows to test and validate new methods and tools.

Vin-Q aims to initiate global transition to regenerative agriculture through a collective action of distributed research

H. Describe the VIN-Q stakeholder groups

The stakeholders identified in the CFC project include cross-discipline experts: scientists and other researchers, farming/growing and food industry experts, local/ regional members including (non-farming) land owners, public administration, tourism and property management. A single individual commonly held more than one stakeholder role.

I. How did VIN-Q synchronize communication and collaborative actions?

Testing the prototype App took place within the context of a comprehensive suite of on-site research actions. The dates of user engagement coincided with three on-site dates for VIN-Q research activities on 12, 17, 19 April 2023. On those visits three independent researchers attended representing their research projects (descentralise research approach) and one of those researchers took samples for 5 additional researchers (distributed research approach). The CFC VIN-Q App was presented as one of those projects to a total of 11 wine-growers during the on-site visits. Those were part of 4 large cooperatives in the Catalanian region, Unio, Domenys, Vallformosa i La Granada and therefore representatives of these organisations attended to the on-site visits. The App prototype was sent to them on an e-mail and they were asked to circulate it within the cooperative network. In addition, the prototype was added to the VIN-Q website and feedback was sought from pre-qualified community members.

The App testing with VIN-Q content and VIN-Q ecosystem members, was co-designed with senior researchers at URV who co-ordinate the VIN-Q initiative. These project leaders explained that the App sought to facilitate trusted content-sharing about regenerative agriculture and novel practices that will be field-tested, with farmers and growers for impact and success.

Participants were invited to browse the VIN-Q app prototype in either of two ways:

- A click-through prototype version, or

- An interactive, navigable prototype, and finally,
- to complete a feedback form.

Fig. 7. Examples of content in the VIN-Q app prototype. SOURCE: VIN-Q (2023)

All content was provided by the expert research team led by Prof. Vladimir Baulin at URV, translated into the Catalan language with the support of Dr. Silvia Planella Conrado.

Fig. 8. Images from the VIN-Q field research days. SOURCE: VIN-Q (2023)

D. Describe VIN-Q as a digital farming collective.

The VIN-Q project aims to develop a digital farming community through a self-governed platform where wine growers, scientist and service providers can advance their knowledge of regenerative agriculture through collaboration opportunities. Currently, the project has garnered interest

from over 200 farmers, with a majority being members of cooperatives.

VIN-Q research shows a fragmented approach to the use of IT for knowledge transfer and collaboration. The ecosystem still relies greatly on in-person meetings and offline channels to share information and access to latest advances in the area of regenerative agriculture. Furthermore, how winemakers organize themselves and communicate vary depending on their affiliations (e.g. cooperatives). Depending on the practices and stage of involvement with regenerative agriculture, their information sources (online and offline), decision-making approaches and learning processes differ.

The experts consulted by VIN-Q agree that in regenerative agriculture a ‘one-size-fits-all’ approach will not suffice. And therefore, there is an increasing value in harvesting interdisciplinary data to make evidence-based decisions for specific situations (type of vine, soil, weather conditions, etc.). However, there are opportunities of collaboration as similar conditions can take place on a global scale, but the challenge remains on how to access to the relevant information and knowledge.

It has been noted a lack of integration between data collected by farmers, researchers and service providers - as part of their legal obligations, data collected from research initiatives (e.g. private soil analysis, participatory research with universities), and open data (e.g. weather). From our research, there is a clear ‘hunger’ for data farming, a growing need for data integration and an outstanding predisposition for knowledge sharing in the area of regenerative agriculture. VIN-Q aims to address these challenges and provide value to its members.

Currently, the VIN-Q website features the creation of posts, groups, ratings, training courses, and media libraries. The platform allows users to propose experiments, share content related to regenerative agriculture, create groups, design and agree on experiment parameters, host courses related to regenerative agriculture, and provide a tool for researchers to disseminate their research outcomes. All those features are available to the VIN-Q community and aim to support the digital farming collective as a whole. The CFC VIN-Q app is a nice add-on to the community as a knowledge transferring tool but, furthermore, a mechanism to track reputation.

E. What learnings are there from the CFC experiment with the VINQ community?

Feedback and responses to the prototype were important to both the CFC project and to the VIN-Q project as it afforded an opportunity to engage in user centred design, a means to determine optimal ways to share information and facilitate virtual connection between scientific researchers, field researchers and experimenters in all walks of life.

The mobile App is recognised as a valued resource for sharing browsable content, in preparation for in-person and self-started actions on the part of new-community members.

- The App can be used by experts to teach technician to take the samples for further analysis
- There is a need to increase the features of the app - so users have a reason to come back and use it often
- The type of content must be less text heavy as the conditions to look at a smartphone while in a vineyard are not ideal. Therefore, short videos or podcasts would be desirable.
- The app can be used as a means to communicate information about the experiments, giving the farmers a micro-credential for taking part in those experiments and helping them to grow their reputation. Reputation not only based in their current practices but also in their involvement with the community as early adopters and pioneers.
- The app can be used for auditing purposes without the need for an external persona. Evidence-based by uploading images and test results.

Researchers who created the shared content found the opportunity to put information directly into the hands of farmers, an interesting new dimension that would need some time to fully incorporate into their practice. But in general it was a complementary approach, a largely autonomous and unintermediated approach was valued. Though also assistance with design and content presentation was considered desirable.

V. Urban Hedgerow case study

J. Describe the mission (common purpose) of Urban Hedgerow project

The Urban Hedgerow project is a Sustainable Cities initiative in Dublin City [20]. It grew from an activist resident community within the locale keen to see a greener urban environment, and who sought to cooperate with owners and managers of publicly held land or property constituting or abutting the realm and to assert community

priorities over those of road users. The initiative has succeeded in creating a 75m Urban Hedgerow on top of a single-story carpark, providing a supportive ecosystem for wildlife, pollinators and a more pleasant, healthy environment for human users.

Fig. 9. Urban Hedgerow project - Concept drawing. SOURCE: UH (2021)

It is an open innovation response to urban biodiversity loss. It poses a challenge to expert, non-expert and cross-disciplinary stakeholders to communicate and cooperate in order to forge impactful solutions to urban biodiversity loss.

K. Describe the Urban Hedgerow stakeholder groups

The stakeholders in the Urban Hedgerow ecosystem are local residents and citizens, education providers, environmental and horticultural scientists, private land owners and public realm managers.

The Urban Hedgerow is a ‘community of participation’, learning and sharing knowledge to identify and enact measurable actions in the urban fabric to enhance native species biodiversity and support insects and wild life in the contested and hostile environment of a modern city.

Urban Hedgerow partners with Phibsboro Biodiversity Group, Shandon Sustainability Group, @PhibsTidyTowns, @ConnectingCabra, @CabraTidyTown, Cabra Youth Community Garden, Phibsboro Mens Shed and The Bohemian Way.

L. How did Urban Hedgerow synchronize communication and collaborative actions?

Testing the prototype App, with Urban Hedgerow content and Urban Hedgerow ecosystem members. Participants were invited to browse the Urban Hedgerow app prototype in either of two ways:

- A click-through prototype version, or
- An interactive, navigable prototype, and finally,
- to complete a feedback form.

All content was provided by the Urban Hedgerow marketing team led by Saad Shahid at Local Green Initiative.

D. Describe Urban Hedgerow as a digital grower collective.

Urban Hedgerow is a digital grower collective in that it uses free virtual communication tools to communicate internally, participate in other local groups and share information with the public (Whats App, Instagram and Twitter).

The ecosystem had already engaged with Web3 technologies to generate ‘art NFTs’ that captured individual efforts during the installation period of the 73m long hedgerow. These are publicly available on Open Sea marketplace where the images captured are anonymised and presented as ‘proofs’ of participation by members.

Urban Hedgerow - Phibsboro Tower collectables are the first series of proofs for contributors to document climate action taken in their locale. The Urban Hedgerow collectables reward participation by issuing proofs-of-work (PoW), proofs-of-existence (PoE) or proofs-of-play (PoP) as NFTs in partnership with the Local Green Initiative. View collection of Urban Hedgerow - Phibsboro Tower on Open Sea [here](#) [21]. Fig. 4. shows the Urban Hedgerow proofs-of-work (PoW) collectables on Open Sea NFT marketplace.

E. What learnings are there from the CFC experiment with the Urban Hedgerow community?

Feedback and responses to the prototype were important to both the CFC and Urban Hedgerow projects as it afforded an opportunity to engage in user centred design, a means to determine optimal ways to share information and facilitate virtual connection between community leaders, urban biodiversity activists.

The CFC app was somewhat suited to internal communication needs but not to external partner interests. Project members did express a desire for a digital learning toolkit, but in general the community preferred in-person, side-by-side apprenticeship style-knowledge transfer: where questions about growing success, native species diversity, and tailoring plant lists to urban wildlife needs and opportunities could naturally emerge.

Fig. 10. Urban Hedgerow proofs-of-work (PoW) collectables on Open Sea NFT marketplace. SOURCE: UH (2022)

The content included in the app was better suited to external partners, however those partners did not feel motivated to download an app to learn about what another project achieved when they could read about it on social media.

Fig. 11. Urban Hedgerow anonymised proofs-of-work (PoW) portraits SOURCE: UH (2022)

All participants were intrigued and felt validated by the collectibles issued to capture and prove participation. All participants welcomed the discrete semi-anonymity afforded by the filter effect used to protect their privacy, in particular that of children.

Subsequent to the test phase, members established a wish list of new digital content: Native species and biodiversity ‘how to’ videos to be prepared with grower experts at the Botanical Gardens education centre [22].

- Woody perennial propagation
- Timely division of herbaceous perennial plant stock
- *Prunus canina* - native fragrant specimens
- Planting for pollinators - balconies, beds and baskets
- Urban microclimates: the concrete jungle
- Water-conserving planting schemes
- Native planting schemes for deep shade

The content will be disseminated on public web and social channels. Another Web3 POW campaign will be launched to support the initiative and capture social-reputation ‘proofs’ of achievement, where members demonstrate success in any of the knowledge fields.

VI. Conclusions and further work

These ecosystems are early-adoptive, and bound by a shared sense of common purpose. Challenges included synchronizing communication and collaborative actions within the new context of hybrid-virtual farming and re-wilding scenarios.

One notable effect of engagement within the communities was how each participant viewed their own expertise and contribution and that of others; influencers, advocates, activists, champions or pioneers.

The VIN-Q ecosystem offered an opportunity to examine reputation and cooperative norms as vectors for cohesion. The Urban Hedgerow project offered insight into competition as a limiting factor in knowledge transfer.

This extended to how trustworthy, reputable or reliable the information shared by each participant was considered. The remote-hybrid nature of communications and knowledge-sharing led to a reordering of existing social roles and those with adaptive personalities, online social networking skills and smart-phone proficiency were able to adapt to the emergent context quite well.

Further work includes further involvement of users in design and more indepth analysis of value and impact of tokenising reputation in emerging innovation ecosystems

and how incentives motivate impact-generating collective climate actions.

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